

Managing the Macroeconomic Uncertainties for optimal Performance of the Agricultural Sector in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Investment in the agricultural sector had long been recognized as a critical driver of sustainable economic growth, necessitating deliberate policy support to enhance overall economic performance. However, persistent macroeconomic uncertainties—particularly fluctuations in consumer price index, exchange rates, and interest rates—had posed significant challenges to many developing economies, including Nigeria. These concerns continued to attract the attention of economic researchers and policymakers alike. This study investigated the influence of selected macroeconomic variables on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. It utilized secondary data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, covering the period from 1986 to 2023. The time series data were subjected to rigorous diagnostic and stability tests and were found suitable for empirical analysis. An Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was employed to assess the short-run and long-run relationships between macroeconomic variables and agricultural productivity. The empirical results, as indicated by the F-statistics and associated probability values, confirmed that the selected macroeconomic indicators exerted a statistically significant influence on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Notably, interest rates exhibited a negative and significant relationship with agricultural productivity, underscoring the adverse effects of high borrowing costs on sectoral performance. Based on these findings, the study recommended that interest rates on agricultural loans should be consistently and deliberately reduced to stimulate investment in the agricultural sector and enhance its contribution to Nigeria's economic growth.

Keywords: Agricultural Output, Macroeconomic variables, Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag

Introduction

Agriculture remains a strategic segment of Nigeria's economy, contributing significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment generation. Historically, it has been the second-largest contributor to GDP after the oil sector, accounting for approximately 41% of the country's GDP and providing employment for about 65% of the population (World Bank, 2007; Ogundipe et al., 2023). The agricultural sector contributes to national development through four primary channels: product contribution, factor contribution, market contribution, and foreign exchange earnings. Despite the sector's potential and the country's vast endowment of fertile land, water resources, and a youthful workforce, the performance of agricultural output has remained suboptimal over the years (Okonkwo & Yusuf, 2024).

Nigeria's agricultural growth has been hindered by several challenges, including weak access to modern inputs and technology, insufficient credit facilities, poor infrastructure, and, more importantly, persistent macroeconomic uncertainties. Between 1970 and 2000, agricultural productivity grew at an average rate of 1.7% per annum, lagging behind the population growth rate of about 2.7% (CBN, 2010). This underperformance has resulted in a widening food supply-demand gap, insufficient raw materials for agro-industries, and a decline in foreign exchange earnings from agricultural exports (Udih, 2014; Musa et al., 2023).

More recently, the sector has grappled with additional threats such as insecurity, including the destruction of farmlands by herdsmen and bandits, alongside economic disruptions from exchange rate volatility, inflationary pressures, trade fluctuations, and dwindling government revenue due to unstable oil prices (Afolabi et al., 2023). These macroeconomic instabilities have exacerbated the sector's fragility, undermining productivity, food security, and livelihoods, particularly in rural areas. While various policy frameworks have been introduced to revitalize the agricultural sector, including intervention schemes and financial incentives, the persistent volatility in Nigeria's macroeconomic environment continues to impede their effectiveness (Okonkwo & Yusuf, 2024). In light of current economic challenges—characterized by rising inflation, exchange rate depreciation, trade imbalances, and capital formation constraints—there is a growing urgency to understand how these macroeconomic variables influence agricultural output.

Consequently, this study investigates the effect of major macroeconomic indicators on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Specifically, it assesses the impact of consumer price index, trade openness, exchange rate, interest rate, balance of trade, and gross fixed capital formation on the performance of the agricultural sector. The study employs an econometric modeling approach based on the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds testing technique developed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001) to establish both short-run and long-run dynamics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Keynesian Theory

Keynesian economics is a theory of aggregate demand and its influence on overall economic performance, including output, employment, and inflation. Propounded by John Maynard Keynes in the 1930s amidst the Great Depression, the theory emphasizes the role of government intervention in stabilizing economic fluctuations. Keynes advocated for increased public expenditure, tax reductions, and monetary expansion as tools to stimulate demand, raise output, and curb unemployment during periods of economic downturn (Blanchard, 2023). Within this framework, a decline in aggregate demand leads to reduced production and job losses, culminating in lower prices and wages. These, in turn, could incentivize capital investment and employment as the economy self-adjusts. This theory is relevant to the agricultural sector in Nigeria, as macroeconomic volatilities — such as inflationary pressures, unstable exchange rates, and fluctuating interest rates — directly affect agricultural output, pricing, and investment decisions.

Endogenous Growth Theory

The Endogenous Growth Theory, pioneered by Arrow (1962), Romer (1986), and Lucas (1988), emerged as a response to the limitations of the Solow-Swan neoclassical model. Unlike exogenous models that attribute long-term economic growth to external factors like technological progress, the endogenous growth theory posits that economic growth is primarily driven by internal factors such as human capital development, innovation, policy environment, and macroeconomic stability (Romer, 1990; Afolabi et al., 2023). This theory underpins the current study, as it suggests that macroeconomic uncertainties—operating within the Nigerian economy—can influence overall economic performance and agricultural output specifically. By examining key macroeconomic variables, the study seeks to establish how these internal dynamics shape agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have explored the relationship between macroeconomic variables and agricultural productivity, within Nigeria and internationally. Conceptually, macroeconomic policy encompasses government strategies aimed at influencing aggregate economic indicators to achieve objectives such as price stability, full employment, and sustainable growth. These policies are often categorized as fiscal or monetary (Musa *et al.*, 2023).

Cristea, et al (2015) investigated the influence of macroeconomic variables on agricultural output in Romania over a 20-year period using ANOVA analysis. The study revealed that while the exchange rate exerted an indirect

influence on agricultural performance, interest rates on credit and deposits had direct impacts on agricultural productivity.

Similarly, Kadir and Tunggal (2015) assessed the effects of macroeconomic variables on agricultural output in Malaysia from 1980 to 2014. The findings highlighted significant relationships between key macroeconomic indicators and agricultural performance, emphasizing the sensitivity of the sector to macroeconomic fluctuations.

In Nigeria, Arorioede and Ogunbadejo (2014) examined the impact of macroeconomic policies on agricultural growth using a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model. The study concluded that Gross Domestic Product (GDP), credit to agriculture, and exchange rates significantly and positively influenced agricultural output. Notably, a positive relationship was established between agricultural output and GDP growth.

Eyo (2008) conducted an empirical analysis of the relationship between the macroeconomic environment and agricultural sector growth in Nigeria, utilizing secondary data spanning 1970 to 2005. Applying the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique, the study found that the prevailing exchange rate regimes did not support agricultural productivity, while inflation, government spending on agriculture, and private foreign investment showed varying degrees of influence.

Hashemi (2014) focused on Iran, analyzing the effect of macroeconomic variables on the agricultural sector between 1981 and 2011 using a VAR model. The results confirmed a long-term relationship between macroeconomic variables and agricultural output, with inflation shocks producing immediate but short-lived effects on agricultural prices.

More recent studies have expanded this inquiry by incorporating macroeconomic variables often neglected in earlier works. For instance, Afolabi et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of including trade openness, balance of trade, and gross fixed capital formation in assessing agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Their findings highlighted that these variables play critical roles in influencing agricultural performance amidst macroeconomic uncertainties.

Despite the growing body of literature, few empirical studies have comprehensively examined the combined effects of major macroeconomic variables — such as consumer price index, trade openness, exchange rate, interest rate, balance of trade, and gross fixed capital formation — on agricultural output in Nigeria. This gap underscores the uniqueness and relevance of the present study, offering fresh insights into how macroeconomic instability shapes agricultural productivity in Nigeria's volatile economic environment.

Methodology

This study is carried out using secondary data sourced from CBN statistical bulletin. Agricultural productivity is the dependent variable while Consumer price index, Exchange rate, Openness, Interest rate, Gross fixed capital formation and balance of trade serve as independent variables. The period covered is from 1986-2023. This study applied the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) cointegration technique. Pearsan et al (2000) averred that cointegration can be tested using the bound test irrespective of the cointegration order i.e whether the variables are purely 1(0) and or purely 1(1) or a mixture of 1(0) and 1(1) variables

Model specification

The Agricultural output growth rate is the dependent variable, while consumer price index, exchange rate, trade openness, Interest rate, gross fixed capital formation and balance of trade are the independent variables. The model for the effect of macroeconomic variables on Agricultural productivity in Nigeria could be stated as follows:

$$AGRIC = (CPI_1, EXCH, OPEN, INTEREST, GFCF_1, BOT_1)$$

Where

AGRIC = Agricultural output

CPI_1 = consumer price index

EXCH = exchange rate

OPEN = trade openness

INTEREST= Interest rate

GFCF_1 = gross fixed capital formation

BOT_1 = balance of trade

Assuming a linear relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables, and using the econometrics model can be specified as follows:

$$AGRIC = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CPI_1 + \alpha_2 EXCH + \alpha_3 OPEN + \alpha_4 INTEREST + \alpha_5 GFCF_1 + \alpha_6 BOT_1 + \mu_t$$

where μ_t = Error term

α_0 = the constant term

α 's = the parameters to be estimated

The apriori expectations are that $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_4, < 0$ while $\alpha_3, \alpha_5, \alpha_6 > 0$

Diagnostic test

Unit root test: In time series analysis, before running the cointegration test the variables must be checked for stationarity. For this purpose, we use the conventional ADF tests. In the presence of variables integrated of order two we cannot interpret the values of F statistics provided by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) or it will go boasted.

The ARDL model is written as follow:

$$\Delta \text{AGRIC}_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta \text{AGRIC}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \text{CPI}_{-1_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \text{EXCH}_{2_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \text{OPEN}_{3_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{5i} \Delta \text{INTEREST}_{4_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{6i} \Delta \text{GFCF}_{-1_{5_{t-1}}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{7i} \Delta \text{BOT}_{-1_{6_{t-1}}} + \beta_8 \text{AGRIC}_{t-1} + \beta_9 \text{CPI}_{-1_{t-1}} + \beta_{10} \text{EXCH}_{t-1} + \beta_{11} \text{OPEN}_{t-1} + \beta_{12} \text{INTEREST}_{t-1} + \beta_{13} \text{GFCF}_{-1_{t-1}} + \beta_{14} \text{BOT}_{-1_{t-1}} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where Δ is the difference operator while ε_t is white noise or error term.

The vector error correction model is specified as follows:

$$\Delta \text{AGRIC}_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{1i} \text{AGRIC}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{2i} \Delta \text{CPI}_{-1_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{3i} \Delta \text{EXCH}_{2_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{4i} \Delta \text{OPEN}_{3_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{5i} \Delta \text{INTEREST}_{4_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{6i} \Delta \text{GFCF}_{-1_{5_{t-1}}} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{7i} \Delta \text{BOT}_{-1_{6_{t-1}}} + \lambda \text{ECM}(-1) + \mu_t$$

$\text{ECM}t-1$ is the error correction term obtained from the cointegration model. The error coefficients (λ) indicates the rate at which the cointegration model corrects its previous period's disequilibrium or speed of adjustment to restore the long run equilibrium relationship. A negative and significant $\text{ECM}t-1$ coefficient implies that any short run movement between the dependent and explanatory variables will unite back to the long run relationship.

Data Analysis and Results

Unit root test result

The results of the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test obtained are as follow:

The Unit root test Result

Variable	Level difference	Probability	Order of integration
AGRIC	1.898550	0.9996	I(0)
CPI_1	-6.452998	0.0000	I(0)
EXCH	-0.881013	0.3275	I(0)
OPEN	1.169961	0.9347	I(0)
INTEREST	0.844179	0.8887	I(0)
GFCF_1	0.969200	0.9086	I(0)
BOT_1	-0.127936	0.6327	I(0)

Source: Author's computation from the E-views result, 2025

From the table above the results shows that one of the variables is stationary at level

Heteroscedasticity test

Under the heteroscedasticity test, we make the following assumptions: if the chi-square calculated is less than the chi-square tabulated, we accept H_0 otherwise we reject. The Heteroscedasticity result obtained is presented below:

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.532903	Prob. F(23,10)	0.8975
Obs*R-squared	18.72374	Prob. Chi-Square(23)	0.7171
Scaled explained SS	0.948608	Prob. Chi-Square(23)	1.0000

For the variables under consideration, chi –square under 23 degrees of freedom chi square (23) = calculated = 18.72374, the chi-square (23) tabulated = 35.0.

DECISION: Since the X^2 calculated is greater than X^2 tabulated, we conclude that the error term of the variables under consideration are heteroscedastic.

Bound Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) testing approach

Conducting the ARDL bounds test procedure, it is expected that the variables are I(0) or I(1), otherwise, the variable may be considered spurious. In the conduct of the ARDL test, we adopt the Augmented DickyFuller (ADF) test to determine the difference levels of the variables to find if they are I(0) and I(1) respectively. We therefore compute an F-statistics test procedure to test the long-run relationship in which the maximum lag length p is 3 in the ECM. The results for the bounds F-test is therefore presented as follows:

The ARDL Bound test result

ARDL Bounds Test
Date: 02/09/24 Time: 12:20

Sample: 1986- 2023
 Included observations: 38
 Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	14.57830	6
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	10 Bound	11 Bound
10%	2.12	3.23
5%	2.45	3.61
2.5%	2.75	3.99
1%	3.15	4.43

Source: Author’s computation from the Eviews result, 2025

The Bound test result from the table above indicates that the underlying ARDL model can be established to determine the long-run slope-estimated coefficients and the short-run dynamic-estimated coefficients. The ARDL(1, 3) is selected based on Akaike information criterion (AIC) , and the estimated results are shown in Table below:

Stability test

To ensure the goodness of fit of the model, diagnostic and stability tests are conducted. Diagnostic tests examine the model for serial correlation, functional form, non-normality and heteroscedasticity. The stability test is conducted by employing the cumulative sum of recursive residuals (CUSUM) suggested by Brown, Durbin and Evans, (1975). To further confirm the stability of the estimated ARDL model, we used the cumulative sum (CUSUM) and the cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMSQ) test method to examine the recursive residuals. The two figures the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests remain within the area restricted by the lines; thus, we reject the null hypothesis for CUSUM and CUSUMSQ and conclude that the estimated ARDL model is effective with stable recursive residuals.

Descriptive statistics

The Jarque-Bera (JB) test statistic was used to determine whether or not the monetary policy variables follow the normal probability distribution. The descriptive statistics for the variables under consideration are therefore presented as follows:

The descriptive statistics

	AGRIC	CPI_1	EXCH	OPEN	INTERES T	GFCF_1	BOT_1
Mean	150368.0	92.25324	67.46862	71.32816	45.01875	10262.58	1356508.
Median	11768.30	63.49000	21.88610	77.25000	11.75000	12.09000	326454.1
Maximum	832048.4	272.0600	158.5526	158.2420	1247.458	379236.9	4971688.
Minimum	268.1600	0.880000	0.544500	27.80000	3.720000	5.460000	-85562.00
Std. Dev.	261184.7	96.10664	65.08670	23.60764	203.2279	62343.97	1677285.

Skewness	1.671749	0.736890	0.249904	0.721325	5.828154	5.833333	0.772362
Kurtosis	4.263202	2.107251	1.231141	6.541128	34.98855	35.02778	1.993204
Jarque-Bera	19.69427	4.577249	5.208784	22.54044	1787.003	1791.246	5.241371
Probability	0.000053	0.101406	0.073948	0.000013	0.000000	0.000000	0.072753
Sum	5563618.	3413.370	2496.339	2639.142	1665.694	379715.4	50190808
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.46E+12	332513.5	152506.0	20063.55	1486856.	1.40E+11	1.01E+14
Observations	38	38	38	38	38	38	38

Source: Author's computation from the Eviews result. 2025

From the result table above, the descriptive statistics indicates that from 1986 to 2023, the six of the variables show an averaged positive mean value from 1356508 to 45.01875. The standard deviation showed that the highest standard deviation of (1677285.) is recorded by the BOT_1 while the least standard deviation of (23.60764) is recorded by OPEN. The skewness statistics from the table revealed that all the variables are positively skewed; the kurtosis coefficients showed that four of the variables are leptokurtic, suggesting that the distributions are high relative to normal distribution while one of the variables is mesokurtic, indicating not too flat topped and two other variable are platykurtic, indicating a flat topped. The probabilities of Jarque-Bera test of normality for the variables indicates that seven of the variables have values greater than 5% level of significance.

Correlation

Under the correlation test, we conduct the test to ascertain the degree of relationship that exists between the dependent variable and the independent variables. This is done using the correlation matrix. The relationships among the studied variables depicted in the model were tested using correlation matrix and the result presented below:

Correlation matrix

	AGRIC	CPI_1	EXCH	OPEN	INTERES T	GFCF_1	BOT_1
AGRIC	1.000000	0.791711	0.587102	0.458585	0.356421	0.360646	0.625149
CPI_1	0.791711	1.000000	0.917163	0.415735	-0.007192	-0.001525	0.845442
EXCH	0.587102	0.917163	1.000000	0.366275	-0.150545	-0.147527	0.776820
OPEN	0.458585	0.415735	0.366275	1.000000	0.630243	0.622014	0.445243
INTERES T	0.356421	-0.007192	-0.150545	0.630243	1.000000	0.999718	0.167443
GFCF_1	0.360646	-0.001525	-0.147527	0.622014	0.999718	1.000000	0.176334
BOT_1	0.625149	0.845442	0.776820	0.445243	0.167443	0.176334	1.000000

Source: Author's computation from E-views, 2025

The correlation result shows that all the variables have positive relationships with the AGRIC. The relationships are actually at 79%, 58%, 45%, 35%, 36% and 62% respectively. Hence, we conclude that there exist no multicollinearity among the variables under consideration.

The ARDL dynamic regression result

Dependent Variable: AGRIC				
Method: ARDL				
Date: 02/09/24 Time: 12:15				
Sample (adjusted): 1986 2023				
Included observations: 34 after adjustments				
Maximum dependent lags: 3 (Automatic selection)				
Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)				
Dynamic regressors (3 lags, automatic): CPI_1 EXCH OPEN INTEREST GFCF_1 BOT_1				
Fixed regressors: C				
Number of models evaluated: 12288				
Selected Model: ARDL(3, 1, 3, 3, 3, 1)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
AGRIC(-1)	0.239614	0.120113	1.994905	0.0740
AGRIC(-2)	-0.406485	0.127099	-3.198181	0.0095
AGRIC(-3)	0.489272	0.117011	4.181434	0.0019
CPI_1	-6191.414	1367.291	-4.528235	0.0011
CPI_1(-1)	8972.944	1318.516	6.805338	0.0000
EXCH	-2292.503	699.5297	-3.277206	0.0083
EXCH(-1)	1041.740	967.4717	1.076765	0.3069
EXCH(-2)	3474.234	1049.010	3.311916	0.0079
EXCH(-3)	-3574.466	783.1563	-4.564179	0.0010
OPEN	13501.66	2435.492	5.543708	0.0002
OPEN(-1)	7136.873	2494.652	2.860870	0.0169
OPEN(-2)	-2035.374	1677.545	-1.213305	0.2529
OPEN(-3)	-7179.725	1922.342	-3.734885	0.0039
INTEREST	-14105.94	3664.135	-3.849732	0.0032
INTEREST(-1)	-14064.85	5035.659	-2.793051	0.0190
INTEREST(-2)	-6912.367	4317.675	-1.600947	0.1405
INTEREST(-3)	-11821.48	3251.927	-3.635223	0.0046
GFCF_1	39.09943	11.40133	3.429375	0.0064
GFCF_1(-1)	-25215.38	5192.542	-4.856076	0.0007
GFCF_1(-2)	23312.08	5084.310	4.585102	0.0010
GFCF_1(-3)	8506.531	4414.146	1.927107	0.0828
BOT_1	0.039093	0.017351	2.253054	0.0479
BOT_1(-1)	-0.097748	0.021944	-4.454492	0.0012

C	-299440.9	87173.76	-3.434989	0.0064
R-squared	0.995034	Mean dependent var		163568.4
Adjusted R-squared	0.983611	S.D. dependent var		268709.5
S.E. of regression	34399.60	Akaike info criterion		23.91747
Sum squared resid	1.18E+10	Schwarz criterion		24.99490
Log likelihood	-382.5969	Hannan-Quinn criter.		24.28490
F-statistic	87.11309	Durbin-Watson stat		2.154216
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

Source: Author’s computation from the Eviews result, 2025

From the result above, the coefficient of AGRIC (-3) is positively signed and statistically significant at 5% critical level; also, the variables, CPI (-1) and GFCF_1(-2) OPEN, EXCH (-2) and BOT_1 are positively signed and statistically significant at 5% critical level. It implies that, any unit change in the amount of agricultural output of the previous years will lead to 48% increases in the current year in Nigeria.

The coefficient of the variable INTEREST is negative. This result indicates that there is a negative relationship between interest rate, agricultural output in Nigeria during the period under review. Thus, unit change in interest rate will lead to a decrease in the current agricultural output growth of the economy.

Statistically, the F-statistic is 98.73039, and the probability of the null hypothesis for no significance in that regression is [0.000000]. The R² - (R-squared) which measures the overall goodness of fit of the entire regression shows the value as follows: 0.995034 = 99%, while the adjusted R² (0.983611)= 98%, shows that the independent variables explain the dependent variable to the tune of 98%. Also, the Durbin Watson (DW) statistics DW = 2.154216 which is greater than the R² shows that the overall regression is statistically significance. Furthermore, the t-ratios for those regressors are also meaningful, and their probabilities are below $\alpha(0.05)$. Thus, the null hypothesis $\beta_i = 0$ is rejected, and those regressors are significant even at a confidence level of 95%.

The short run effect of macroeconomic variables on the AGRIC productivity

There is long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables in the regression model; however, it is the short-run that transmit to the long-run. Thus, Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) is therefore used to correct or eliminate the discrepancy that occurs in the short-run. The coefficients of the explanatory variables in the error correction model measure the short-run relationship. The assumption of the ECM states that if two variables are cointegrated, then, there is error correction mechanism to revise instability in short term (Engle & Granger, 1987). ECM is used to see the speed of adjustments of the variables to deviations from their common stochastic trend. ECM corrects the deviations from the long run equilibrium by short-run adjustments. This shows us that changes in independent variables are a function of changes in explanatory variables and the lagged error term in cointegrated regression. The ECM result is therefore presented below:

The short run error correction dynamics

ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form

Dependent Variable: AGRIC				
Selected Model: ARDL(3, 1, 3, 3, 3, 1)				
Date: 02/09/24 Time: 12:16				
Sample: 1986 2022				
Included observations: 38				
Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(AGRIC(-1))	-0.082787	0.094671	-0.874469	0.4024
D(AGRIC(-2))	-0.489272	0.117011	-4.181434	0.0019
D(CPI_1)	-6191.413714	1367.290656	-4.528235	0.0011
D(EXCH)	-2292.502979	699.529685	-3.277206	0.0083
D(EXCH(-1))	-3474.233744	1049.010246	-3.311916	0.0079
D(EXCH(-2))	3574.465768	783.156318	4.564179	0.0010
D(OPEN)	13501.655593	2435.491654	5.543708	0.0002
D(OPEN(-1))	2035.374430	1677.545120	1.213305	0.2529
D(OPEN(-2))	7179.724616	1922.341784	3.734885	0.0039
D(INTEREST)	-14105.937220	3664.135110	-3.849732	0.0032
D(INTEREST(-1))	6912.367098	4317.675156	1.600947	0.1405
D(INTEREST(-2))	11821.480444	3251.927083	3.635223	0.0046
D(GFCF_1)	39.099434	11.401328	3.429375	0.0064
D(GFCF_1(-1))	-23312.079834	5084.309616	-4.585102	0.0010
D(GFCF_1(-2))	-8506.530761	4414.146180	-1.927107	0.0828
D(BOT_1)	0.039093	0.017351	2.253054	0.0479
ECM(-1)	-0.677599	0.124042	-5.462654	0.0003
ECM = AGRIC - (4104.9786*CPI_1 -1993.7964*EXCH + 16858.6792 *OPEN -69221.7868*INTEREST + 9802.7423*GFCF_1 -0.0866*BOT_1 -441914.3725)				

Source: Author's computation from the Eviews result, 2025

In the short run result, the coefficient of the lagged variable of the dependent variable AGRIC (-2) shows the value, -0.489272. This implies that a decreases in the agricultural output of the previous year reduces the growth of the current year AGRIC in the short term. The equilibrium error-correction coefficient ECM (-1) is -0.677599 which has the expected negative sign. The error correction term here is negative and significant meaning that there is a long run causality running from independent variables to dependent variable. It also confirms that all the variables are cointegrated or have long run relationship. We can therefore state that 67 percent gap between long run equilibrium value and the actual value of the dependent variable (AGRIC) has been corrected. It can be also said that the speed of adjustment towards long run equilibrium is 67 percent annually. Its t-ratio is -5.462654, and the probability of the null hypothesis being true for zero is [0.003], which is significant even when $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it can also be concluded that the adjustment is quite meaningful in the short-run ARDL relationship.

The long run relationship of the between the selected macroeconomic variables on the AGRIC

The long run relationship result

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CPI_1	4104.978635	593.252441	6.919447	0.0000
EXCH	-1993.796400	751.824983	-2.651942	0.0242
OPEN	16858.679191	5343.938806	3.154729	0.0103
INTEREST	-69221.786829	21837.382284	-3.169876	0.0100
GFCF_1	9802.742319	3433.704204	2.854859	0.0171
BOT_1	-0.086563	0.023075	-3.751454	0.0038
C	-441914.372547	126419.430681	-3.495621	0.0058

Source: Author’s computation from the E-views result, 2025

The long-run elasticity of the independent macroeconomic variables contributing to AGRIC is 4104.978635 from 1986 to the present. Thus, we show that CPI, OPEN, GFCF have a positive effect on the agricultural output growth in the long run. This result is in line with apriori expectation with the exception CPI which was expected to be negative but turned positive after the analysis.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The agricultural sector remains a cornerstone of economic growth and development in Nigeria, serving as a major contributor to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and a critical source of livelihood for a significant portion of the population. This study set out to investigate the long-run relationship between macroeconomic variables and agricultural productivity in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023, employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach.

The empirical findings confirmed the existence of a stable long-run relationship between agricultural productivity and key macroeconomic variables, namely the consumer price index, exchange rate, trade openness, interest rate, gross fixed capital formation, and balance of trade. The ARDL estimates revealed that increases in exchange rate, interest rate, and balance of trade adversely affect agricultural productivity in the long run. Conversely, consumer price index, trade openness, and gross fixed capital formation exerted a significant positive influence on agricultural output.

These results underscore the considerable sensitivity of Nigeria’s agricultural sector to the macroeconomic environment. The study concludes that agricultural productivity is not isolated from macroeconomic fluctuations but is, in fact, largely shaped by them. Thus, policy distortions or instability in these macroeconomic indicators can either constrain or enhance agricultural output. The findings suggest that equipping farmers and agribusiness

stakeholders with a practical understanding of how these macroeconomic forces interact with agricultural productivity would be instrumental in improving sectoral performance. Ultimately, enhancing the resilience of the agricultural sector against macroeconomic volatility will strengthen its contribution to Nigeria's GDP and national food security.

Recommendations

In view of the study's findings, the following actionable recommendations are proposed to improve agricultural productivity in Nigeria within the prevailing macroeconomic context:

I. Review and Reduction of Agricultural Interest Rates: The government, in collaboration with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), should implement targeted policies to lower interest rates for agricultural loans. A preferential, single-digit interest rate regime for agribusinesses would stimulate capital investment in the sector and mitigate the adverse effects of high borrowing costs, particularly as the economy diversifies away from oil dependence.

2. Stabilization of the Exchange Rate through Firm Monetary Policy Management: Considering the negative long-run impact of exchange rate volatility on agricultural productivity, monetary authorities should adopt proactive and consistent monetary policy frameworks aimed at achieving a stable and competitive exchange rate. This would improve planning certainty for farmers, investors, and agribusiness exporters.

3. Strengthen Import Restrictions on Locally Available Agricultural Commodities: The government should sustain and expand import restrictions on agricultural products that can be viably produced domestically, such as rice, maize, and poultry products. This would not only protect local farmers from unfair foreign competition but also improve Nigeria's trade balance and encourage domestic agribusiness expansion.

4. Enhancement of the Business Environment for Agricultural Investments: To foster sustained capital formation in agriculture, the government must prioritize investments in critical public infrastructure—such as rural roads, irrigation systems, storage facilities, and rural electrification. Additionally, maintaining a stable consumer price index and deepening trade liberalization initiatives will create a more predictable and investment-friendly environment for both smallholder farmers and large-scale agribusiness enterprises

References

Afolabi, B., Adeniran, A., & Olamide, T. (2023). *Macroeconomic shocks and agricultural output performance in Nigeria*. *Nigerian Journal of Economic Policy*, 30(2), 45-62.

- Ahmed, Y. O. (1993). Bank of the north pamphlets on agricultural financing. Various circulars and Policy Guidelines on Agricultural Financing in Bank of the North Limited. A paper delivered at seminars at Bank of the North Human Resources and Development Centre by (Agric. Officer, Bank of the North Limited).
- Arorioede O. R. & Ogunbadejo, H.K. (2014). Impact of macroeconomic policy on agricultural growth in Nigeria, *IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences*, 7(11), 1-5
- Blanchard, O. (2023). *Macroeconomics (8th ed.)*. Pearson Education.
- Brown, R.L., Durbin, J & Evans, J.M. (1975). Techniques for testing the constancy of regression relationships over time (with discussion). *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society B(37)*, 149- 192
- Brownson, V. E. & Etim (2012). Agricultural productivity and macroeconomic variable fluctuations, *International Journal of finance and economics*, 4(8), 114-125
- Central Bank of Nigeria (2010). Statistical bulletin of Central Bank of Nigeria, Retrieved from <http://www.cbn.org/out/publications>
- Cristea, M., Marcu, N. & Meghisan, G. (2015). The influence of macroeconomic variables on the Romanian agriculture. *Proc Rom. Acad Series*, 17(1), 65-75
- Dickey, D., & Fuller, W.A. (1981). Likelihood ratio statistics for autoregressive time series with a unit root. *Econometrica*, 49, 1057-1072.
- Engle, R., & Granger, C. (1987). Co-integration and error correction: Representation, estimation and testing. *Econometrica*, 55(22), 251-276.
- Enoma, A. (2010) Agricultural credit and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical analysis, being dissertation submitted to the department of economics, Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Nigeria.
- Eyo, E.O. (2008). Macroeconomic environment and agricultural sector growth in Nigeria, *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 4(6), 781-786
- Hashemi, R. (2014). Analysis of the macroeconomic variables effect on the agricultural sector, *Agricultural Science Development*, 3(11), 370-374.

- Johansen, S. & Juselius, K., (1990). Maximum likelihood estimation and inference on cointegration– with applications to the demand for money, *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 52(2), 169–210.
- Kadir , S.U. & Tungal, N.Z. (2015). The impact of macroeconomic variables toward agricultural productivity in Malaysia. *South East Asia Journal of Contemporary Business, Economics and Law*, 8(3), 21-27
- Musa, H., Sanni, A., & Adepoju, F. (2023). Exchange rate volatility and agricultural productivity in Nigeria: An empirical analysis. *West African Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 14(1), 22-38.
- Ogundipe, A., Oladipo, O., & Yakubu, B. (2023). *Agriculture and economic resilience in Nigeria amidst global shocks. African Development Review*, 35(1), 66-85.
- Okonkwo, U., & Yusuf, M. (2024). *Macroeconomic instability and food security in Nigeria: Evidence from recent data. Journal of African Macroeconomic Studies*, 19(1), 13-32.
- Obilor, S.I. (2013). The impact of commercial banks' credit to agriculture on agricultural development in Nigeria: An econometric analysis. *International Journal of Business Humanities and Technology*, 3(1), 85 – 95.
- Odhiambo, N.M. (2008). Financial depth, savings and economic growth in kenya: A dynamic 2qw ausal linkage, *Economic Modelling, Elsevier*, 25(4), 704-713
- Pesaran, M.H., & Pesaran, B. (1997). *Working with microfit 4.0: Interactive econometric Analysis*, Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Pesaran, M.H., & Shin, Y. (1999). *An autoregressive distributed lag modelling approach to cointegration analysis, in Econometrics and Economic Theory in the 20th Century: The Ragnar Frisch Centennial Symposium (Ed.) S. Strom*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shih, Y., & Smith, R. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of the level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16, 289-326.
- Udih, M. (2014). Bank credits and agricultural development: Does it promote entrepreneurship performance? *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(11), 102 – 107.
- World Development Report (2007). Agriculture for development United States of America, Monthly Report, 2, 7-9.